

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Sh.Kh.Mamatalieva

CERTAIN ASPECTS OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF PARTICIPANTS IN CRIMINAL
PROCEEDINGS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF BELARUS CRIMINAL PROCEDURAL LAW)

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

zenodo

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

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2023-2024

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